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Research Article

Designing, In Silico Screening and Molecular Docking Studies of Some Novel 5-(4-Bromophenyl)-N-Ethyl-1,3,4-Thiadiazol-2-Amine Derivatives Targeting EGFR Kinase

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ABSTRACT

Lung tumour is prevalent malignancies in population, with (EGFR) serving as critical therapeutic agent as its treatment due to its pivotal role in tumour progression and survival. The present study hypothesises that 5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-ethyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine derivatives exhibit significant binding affinities toward EGFR, thereby representing potential anti-cancer agents. These studies we have Designed thiadiazole analogues gone through “Lipinski's rule of 5”, vebers rule, ADMET screening, drug-likeness. The molecular Docking was conducted via PyRx software to evaluate binding interactions of the synthesised derivatives with EGFR kinase domain. We performed the comparative study of docking between the designed thadiazole derivative and standard anticancer drug erlotinib. We conclude that 26 out of 33 molecule follows Lipinski's rule of five with zero violation, also all compounds successfully passed toxicity assessment. The docking result conclude that the compound SP22, SP23, SP24, SP25, SP26, SP28, SP29, SP30, SP32 and SP33 exhibited highest docking score as compared to standard anticancer drug erlotinib targeting EGFR kinase. Hence these molecules are selected for future synthesis. This study highlights the potential of thiadiazole-based scaffolds in anti-cancer drug design.

INTRODUCTION

Tumour remains threat and life-threatening concerns. Among its various types, lung cancer

stands out as particularly deadly. Kinases, a class of enzymes responsible for transferring phosphate groups, play a pivotal role in numerous cellular functions. Among these, cytoplasmic tyrosine

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kinases are crucial for transmitting external signals into the cell and are often associated with oncogenic processes. As a result, developing inhibitors that specifically target tyrosine kinases is critically important in cancer treatment [1-3].

The development of several strong and TKIs, past 20 years has advanced our knowledge. A molecular target for certain possible cancer treatments has been found to be EGFR. Thirteen secreted polypeptide ligands and EGFR family [4-5].

To address these challenges, extensive research has been conducted to design innovative EGFR inhibitors with enhanced selectivity and efficacy. Among the different chemical frameworks studied, thiadiazole derivatives have shown great promise as biological properties. Modifications such as halogenation and N-methylation have been found to significantly improve their pharmacological activity, particularly against kinases like EGFR[6-8].

In Present study we have to performed computational methodologies. It plays vital role in drug discovery and to minimize the risk of toxicity. In this study, we propose that 5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-ethyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazol-2-amine derivatives exhibit strong EGFR inhibitory activity through specific interactions within the kinase domain. Molecular docking analysis was

employed to evaluate their binding affinities, interaction mechanisms, and structural features. This research aims to identify novel and selective EGFR inhibitors, contributing to the advancement of targeted lung cancer therapies [9].

The standard anticancer drug erlotinib, a tyrosine kinase inhibitor used in the treatment of non-small cell lung cancer and pancreatic cancer, was used for a comparative study with thiadiazole derivatives. The study was conducted based on their binding affinity to the EGFR kinase protein, a key target in cancer therapy[10]

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Designing of 5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-ethyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole-2-amine derivatives

The reaction was achieved by ethyl 4-bromobenzoate react with hydrazine hydrochloride ($\text{NH}_2 \text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{HCL}$) in ethanol under reflux condition to form 4bromobenzohydrazide. Further 4bromobenzohydrazide treated with thiocyanate in ethanol under reflux condition to give 2-[(4-bromophenyl) carbonyl]-N-ethylhydrazinecarbothioamide, further 2-[(4-bromophenyl) carbonyl]-N-ethylhydrazinecarbothioamide is react with concentrated sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) with continuous stirring to form 5(4-bromophenyl)-N-ethyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole-2-amine derivatives.

Design scheme: Synthesis of 5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-ethyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazol-2-amine

Pharmacokinetic and toxicity prediction of designed derivatives

Drug discovery and development heavily relies on chemical ADMET. Also being sufficiently effective against target, drug candidate should have suitable ADMET characteristics at therapeutic dosage. The ADME analysis, drug-likeness, and toxicity parameters of the proposed compounds were evaluated. Swiss ADME servers were used to examine the pharmacokinetic (ADME) properties of proposed derivatives as well as the Lipinski rule of five. ProTox-II has been used to forecast the chemicals' toxicity [11-12].

Molecular Docking

Binding of analogue in active areas of crystal structures of EGFR kinase (T790M/L858R) (PDB DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2210/pdb5EDP/pdb>) were investigated utilising an in-silico process, which

were obtained from www.pdb.org, the Protein Data Bank service. All compound performed docking by PyRx 0.8. Discovery Studio Visualizer (version19) was used to protein preparation. 3D (X= -60.135585, Y= -7.649423, Z= -25.673) was for used to perform docking. BIOVIA Visualizer gave binding information [13].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

All compounds having bioavailability evaluated by using "Lipinski's rule of five" for oral route (Table 2). Pharmacokinetics parameter & drug-likeness properties of compounds are examined by swissADME software (Table 3). The "acute toxicity has been predicted along with LD50 (mg/kg)" by ProTox-II (Table 4). The PyRx software (0.8 version) of molecular docking to produce "active Amino acid residues, bond length, category, type, ligand energies, and scores" of compounds [14-15]. The Comparative study was performed by using standard anticancer drug (Erlotinib) with binding protein EGFR kinase (Table 5-6).

Table 1: Structure, IUPAC name and Molecular formula

Comp.Code	Structure	IUPAC Name	M.F
SP1		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-ethyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ BrN ₃ S
SP2		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-propyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ BrN ₃ S
SP3		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-(propan-2-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ BrN ₃ S
SP4		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-butyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ BrN ₃ S
SP5		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-(2-methylpropyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ BrN ₃ S
SP6		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-(butan-2-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ BrN ₃ S
SP7		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-tert-butyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ BrN ₃ S
SP8		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-pentyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ S
SP9		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-(3-methylbutyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ S
SP10		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-(2,2-dimethylpropyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ S

SP11		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-hexyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ BrN ₃ S
SP12		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-heptyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ BrN ₃ S
SP13		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-octyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ BrN ₃ S
SP14		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-nonyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ BrN ₃ S
SP15		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-decyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ BrN ₃ S
SP16		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-undecyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ BrN ₃ S
SP17		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-dodecyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₂₀ H ₃₀ BrN ₃ S
SP18		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-tridecyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₂₁ H ₃₂ BrN ₃ S
SP19		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-tetradecyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₂₂ H ₃₄ BrN ₃ S
SP20		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-pentadecyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₂₃ H ₃₆ BrN ₃ S

SP21		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ BrN ₃ S
SP22		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-(2-methylphenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ BrN ₃ S
SP23		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-(3-methylphenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ BrN ₃ S
SP24		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-(4-methylphenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ BrN ₃ S
SP25		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-(2-chlorophenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrN ₃ SCl
SP26		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-(3-chlorophenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrN ₃ SCl
SP27		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-(4-chlorophenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrN ₃ SCl
SP28		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-(2-nitrophenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrN ₄ SO ₂

SP29		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-(3-nitrophenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrN ₄ SO ₂
SP30		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-(4-nitrophenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrN ₄ SO ₂
SP31		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-(2-methoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ BrN ₃ SO
SP32		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-(3-methoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ BrN ₃ SO
SP33		5-(4-bromophenyl)-N-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ BrN ₃ SO

Where: IUPAC – International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry, MF – Molecular Formula

Table 2: Lipinski rule of 5, Veber's rule

Compound Code	Lipinski rule of five					Veber's rule	
	MW	Log P	HBA	HBD	Lipinski violation	TPSA	Rotatable Bond
SP1	284.18	2.76	2	1	0	66.05	3
SP2	298.2	2.99	2	1	0	66.05	4
SP3	298.2	2.95	2	1	0	66.05	3
SP4	312.23	3.13	2	1	0	66.05	5
SP5	312.23	3.25	2	1	0	66.05	4
SP6	312.23	3.22	2	1	0	66.05	4
SP7	312.23	3.08	2	1	0	66.05	3
SP8	326.26	3.32	2	1	0	66.05	6
SP9	326.26	3.41	2	1	0	66.05	5
SP10	326.26	3.41	2	1	0	66.05	4
SP11	340.28	3.68	2	1	0	66.05	7
SP12	354.31	3.82	2	1	0	66.05	8
SP13	368.33	4.13	2	1	0	66.05	9
SP14	382.36	4.4	2	1	1	66.05	10
SP15	396.39	4.76	2	1	1	66.05	11
SP16	410.41	4.83	2	1	1	66.05	12

SP17	424.44	5.08	2	1	1	66.05	13
SP18	438.47	5.22	2	1	1	66.05	14
SP19	452.49	5.49	2	1	1	66.05	15
SP20	466.52	5.73	2	1	1	66.05	16
SP21	332.22	2.89	2	1	0	66.05	3
SP22	346.24	3.07	2	1	0	66.05	3
SP23	346.24	3.17	2	1	0	66.05	3
SP24	346.24	3.15	2	1	0	66.05	3
SP25	366.66	3.35	2	1	0	66.05	3
SP26	366.66	3.26	2	1	0	66.05	3
SP27	366.66	3.18	2	1	0	66.05	3
SP28	377.22	2.61	4	1	0	111.87	4
SP29	377.22	2.64	4	1	0	111.87	4
SP30	377.22	2.54	4	1	0	111.87	4
SP31	362.24	3.44	3	1	0	75.28	4
SP32	362.24	3.21	3	1	0	75.28	4
SP33	362.24	3.23	3	1	0	75.28	4

Where: MW- Molecular Weight, HBA - Number of hydrogen bond acceptors, HBD - Number of hydrogen bond donor, TPSA – Total Polar Surface area, Log p - logarithm of compound partition.

Table 3: the pharmacokinetics and drug-likeness Properties of Compound

Code	GI absorption	BBB PER MEANT	Pgp subst rate	CYP 1A2 inhib itor	CYP 2C19 inhib itor	CYP 2C9 inhib itor	CYP 2D6 inhib itor	CYP 3A4 inhib itor	Ghose	Veber	Egan	Muegge	Bioavailability score
SP1	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP2	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP3	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP4	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP5	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP6	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP7	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP8	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP9	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP10	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP11	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	0	0	0	1	0.55
SP12	High	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	0	0	0	1	0.55
SP13	High	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	0	0	0	1	0.55
PS14	High	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	1	0	1	1	0.55
SP15	High	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	1	1	1	1	0.55
SP16	High	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	1	1	1	1	0.55
SP17	Low	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	1	1	1	1	0.55
SP18	Low	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	NO	Yes	1	1	1	1	0.55
SP19	Low	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	NO	Yes	1	1	1	1	0.55
SP20	Low	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	NO	Yes	1	1	1	2	0.55
SP21	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP22	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP23	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP24	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP25	High	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	0	0	0	1	0.55
SP26	High	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	0	0	0	1	0.55
SP27	High	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	0	0	0	1	0.55
SP28	High	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	0	0	0	0	0.55

SP29	High	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP30	High	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP31	High	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP32	High	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	0	0	0	0	0.55
SP33	High	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	0	0	0	0	0.55

Where: GI - gastrointestinal absorption, BBB- blood brain barrier penetration; P-gp - p-glycoprotein

Table 4: The acute toxicity of Compounds

COMP. CODE	LD50 (mg/kg)	Toxicity class	Prediction Accuracy (%)	Hepatotoxicity	Carcinogenicity	Immunotoxicity	Mutagenicity	Cytotoxicity
SP1	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP2	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP3	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP4	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP5	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP6	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP7	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP8	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP9	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP10	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP11	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP12	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP13	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP14	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP15	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP16	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP17	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP18	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP19	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP20	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP21	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP22	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP23	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP24	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP25	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP26	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP27	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP28	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP29	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP30	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP31	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP32	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)
SP33	1190	4	100	A (0.69)	I (0.62)	A (0.96)	I (0.97)	I (0.93)

Where: I- Inactive, A - Active

Table 5: Standard Erlotinib Docking Score and 2D, 3D Images

CODE	ACTIVE AMINO ACID	BOND TYPE	DOCKING SCORE	2D IMAGE	3D IMAGE
Erlotinib	CYS797	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-6.8		
	CYS797	Hydrogen Bond			
	ARG841	Carbon Hydrogen Bond			
	LEU718	Pi-Sigma			
	LEU844	Pi-Sigma			
	MET790	Pi-Sulfur			
	LEU718	Pi-Alkyl			
	ALA743	Pi-Alkyl			
LEU844	Pi-Alkyl				

Table 6: Derivatives Docking Score and 2D, 3D Images

CODE	ACTIVE AMINO ACID	BOND TYPE	DOCKING SCORE	2D Image	3D Image
SP1	LEU778	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-5.8		
	ILE1018	Pi-Cation			
	ARG776	Pi-Anion			
	LEU778	Pi-Sigma			
	ILE1018	Alkyl			
	ARG776	Pi-Alkyl			
SP2	LEU844	Pi-Sigma	-5.8		
	PHE723	Alkyl			
	ALA743	Alkyl			
	LEU718	Pi-Alkyl			
	LEU792	Pi-Alkyl			
	VAL726	Pi-Alkyl			
ALA743	Pi-Alkyl				
SP3	ASP1014	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-6.3		
	ARG705	Carbon Hydrogen Bond			
	ARG776	Pi-Cation			
	ARG705	Alkyl			
	PRO772	Pi-Alkyl			
	ALA1013	Pi-Alkyl			

SP4	LEU778	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	-6.2		
	ARG776	Pi-Cation			
	ASP1014	Pi-Anion			
	LEU778	Pi-Sigma			
	ARG705	Alkyl			
	ILE1018				
	LEU703				
	ARG705				
	ILE1018				
	ALA1013	Pi-Alkyl			
ARG776					
SP5	ASP1014	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-6.2		
	ARG705	Carbon Hydrogen Bond			
	ARG776	Pi-Cation			
	ARG705	Alkyl			
	PRO772				
	ALA1013	Pi-Alkyl			
SP6	ALA1013	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-6.3		
	ARG776	Pi-Cation			
	LEU703	Alkyl			
	ARG705				
	ARG776				
	LEU778	Pi-Alkyl			
	LEU1017				
ARG705					
SP7	ASP1014	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-6.1		
	ARG705	Carbon Hydrogen Bond			
	ARG776	Pi-Cation			
	LEU1017	Pi-Sigma			
	ARG705	Alkyl			
SP8	ARG705	Carbon Hydrogen Bond	-6.1		
	ASP770				
	ARG776	Pi-Cation			
	PRO772	Alkyl			
	ARG705				
	PRO772				
	HIS850	Pi-Alkyl			
ALA1013					

SP9	LEU778	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-6.2		
	ARG776	Pi-Cation			
	ASP770	Pi-Anion			
	ASP1014	Pi-Anion			
	LEU778	Pi-Sigma			
	ILE1018	Alkyl			
	ALA1013	Pi-Alkyl			
ARG776					
SP10	MET793	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-5.9		
	LEU718	Pi-Sigma			
	LEU718				
	MET790	Alkyl			
	LEU844				
ALA743	Pi-Alkyl				
SP11	LEU844	Pi-Sigma	-6.1		
	MET790	Pi-Sulfur			
	ALA743	Alkyl			
	ILE759				
	LEU718				
	LEU792				
	PHE723	Pi-Alkyl			
	PHE723				
	VAL726				
ALA743					
SP12	LYS745	Pi-Cation; Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond	-6.1		
	LEU844	Pi-Sigma			
	MET790	Pi-Sulfur			
	ALA743	Alkyl			
	ILE759				
	LEU718				
	PHE723	Pi-Alkyl			
ALA743					
SP13	LYS745	Pi-Cation; Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond	-6.2		
	LEU844	Pi-Sigma			
	MET766	Pi-Sulfur			
	MET790				
	ALA743	Alkyl			
	LEU747				
	ILE759				
	LEU718				
VAL726					

	ILE1018	Pi-Alkyl			
	LEU703				
	ARG705				
	ILE1018				
	TYR1016				
PRO772					
SP19	GLU758	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-5.9		
	ASP761	Pi-Anion			
	LEU747	Alkyl			
	ILE759	Pi-Alkyl			
	PHE723				
	PHE723				
SP20	SER912	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-5.7		
	PRO934	Alkyl			
	PRO934				
	PRO934				
	PRO934				
	ILE981	Pi-Alkyl			
	TRP905				
	TRP905				
	PHE910				
TYR915					
SP21	ARG776	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-6.6		
	ASP770	Pi-Anion			
	ASP1014				
	LEU1017	Pi-Sigma			
	PRO772	Alkyl			
	LEU778	Pi-Alkyl			
SP22	LYS745	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-6.9		
	ASP855	Pi-Anion			
	LEU844	Pi-Sigma			
	MET790	Pi-Sulfur			
	PHE723	Pi-Pi Stacked			
	ALA743	Alkyl			
	MET793				
	VAL726	Pi-Alkyl			
	ALA743				
SP23	ARG776	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-7.2		
	ASP770	Pi-Anion			
	LEU1017	Alkyl			
	ILE1018				

	PRO772 ALA1013	Pi-Alkyl			
SP24	ARG776	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-7.0		
	ARG705	Carbon Hydrogen Bond			
	ARG776	Pi-Cation			
	PRO772	Alkyl			
	ILE1018				
	ALA1013 PRO772	Pi-Alkyl			
SP25	LEU778	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-7.6		
	ARG776	Pi-Cation			
	ASP770	Pi-Anion			
	ASP1014				
	LEU778	Pi-Sigma			
	ALA1013	Pi-Alkyl			
	ARG705 ARG776				
SP26	LEU718	Pi-Sigma	-6.8		
	LEU844				
	MET790	Pi-Sulfur			
	MET766	Alkyl			
	MET790				
	LEU718				
	LEU718	Pi-Alkyl			
	ALA743 LEU844				
SP27	ASP1012	Pi-Anion	-6.7		
	THR847	Pi-Sigma			
	PHE997	Pi-Sulfur			
	PHE997	Pi-Pi T-shaped			
	PRO992	Alkyl			
	LEU792				
	PRO794				
	PRO992				
	PRO741 PRO794	Pi-Alkyl			

SP28	LEU718	Pi-Sigma	-7.1		
	LEU718	Alkyl			
	LEU718	Pi-Alkyl			
	ALA743				
	LEU844				
	VAL726				
	MET790				
SP29	LYS745	Pi-Cation	-7.3		
	ASP855	Pi-Anion			
	LEU844	Pi-Sigma			
	PHE723	Pi-Pi Stacked			
	VAL726	Pi-Alkyl			
	ALA743				
	MET790				
SP30	LYS745	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-7.1		
	THR854				
	ASP855				
	LEU718	Pi-Sigma			
	LEU718	Alkyl			
	LEU718	Pi-Alkyl			
	ALA743				
	LEU844				
	VAL726				
	MET790				
LEU844					
SP31	ASP855	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-6.4		
	GLU762	Carbon Hydrogen Bond			
	LYS745	Pi-Cation			
	LYS745				
	GLU762	Pi-Anion			
	PHE723	Pi-Sulfur			
	PHE723	Pi-Pi Stacked			
	PHE723	Pi-Pi T-shaped			
	ALA755	Alkyl			
MET766					
SP32	ALA1013	Conventional Hydrogen Bond	-6.9		
	ASP1014	Carbon Hydrogen Bond			
	ARG705	Pi-Cation			
	ARG776				
	ARG776				

	LYS852	Pi-Anion			
	ASP770				
	ASP1014				
	LEU703	Alkyl			
	ARG705				
	ILE1018				
	LEU1017	Pi-Alkyl			
	ARG776				
	ARG705				
SP33	LEU718	Pi-Sigma	-6.9		
	LEU844				
	MET790	Pi-Sulfur			
	LEU718	Pi-Alkyl			
	ALA743				

Where: 2D-Two Dimension, 3D – Three Dimension

CONCLUSION

In this Present work, we designed a series of 33 thiadiazole derivatives as potential anticancer agents targeting EGFR kinase. The ADMET analysis revealed that 26 out of 33 molecules adhered to Lipinski's rule of five with zero violations, indicating their potential as drug-like candidates. Furthermore, all compounds successfully passed the toxicity assessment, suggesting favourable pharmacokinetic and safety profiles.

Molecular docking studies were conducted to evaluate the binding affinity of these thiadiazole derivatives against the EGFR kinase. The docking results demonstrated that compounds SP22, SP23, SP24, SP25, SP26, SP28, SP29, SP30, SP32, and SP33 exhibited higher docking scores compared to the standard anticancer drug Erlotinib, suggesting their potential as promising EGFR inhibitors. These findings indicate that selected thiadiazole derivatives could serve as potential lead compounds for further in vitro and in vivo investigations, aiming to develop novel anticancer agents targeting EGFR

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